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A comparison of environmental and spatially explicit hunting-yield models for continuous gradient of relative abundance of wild boar in Europe

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Abstract

Previous studies have used separate regional models of species distribution and abundance to address shifting species–environment relationships. These models, based on hunting yield data, incorporate regional effects and improve reliability, but they often fail to capture continuous spatial gradients. This report evaluates a new approach for modelling gradual spatial changes in wild boar relative abundance using spatially explicit models. We compared downscaled hunting yield predictions from two models—an environmental-only model and a spatially explicit model—with estimates from the ENETWILD consortium (2022). Hunting yields were modelled using a Negative Binomial framework with covariates and a spatial random effect implemented via a Nearest Neighbour Gaussian Process

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(NNGP), generating predictions on a 10×10 km grid across the species' range. Model performance was assessed by comparing total predicted harvests, uncertainty (credible vs. confidence intervals), spatial agreement (Spearman correlations), and country-level results for Spain, France, Italy, and Poland to account for differences in data resolution. Results indicate that spatial random-effect models produce smooth continental patterns but are limited by non-stationarity and heterogeneous data resolution, leading to unreliable predictions in areas with coarse or uneven spatial units. Environmental and spatial models capture different aspects of wild boar distribution, underscoring the need to explicitly account for regional variability when modelling at a European scale. The ENETWILD-consortium et al. (2024) model, which calibrates hunting bag data into wild boar density estimates, shows the strongest correlation with independent references and is currently the most reliable option for risk assessments that require spatially explicit wild boar density data. High-resolution hunting statistics are critical for producing realistic spatial patterns; where data resolution is low, models generate unreliable results, whereas areas with improved, high-resolution data yield spatial patterns consistent with ecological expectations.

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Key words: wild boar, spatial distribution model, hunting yield, spatial random-effect models

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Summary

Background: The ENETWILD consortium supports European and national authorities by providing spatial modelling tools and evidence for wildlife risk assessment and management. Spatial modelling of wild boar abundance is essential for long-term monitoring and proactive management, which is particularly critical following the recent ASF outbreaks. Previous studies have developed separate regional models of spatial distribution and abundance to address the challenges posed by shifting species-environment relationships. Based on hunting yield (HY) data, these models account for regional effects and provide more reliable estimates. However, regional models may fail to accurately represent continuous spatial gradients. Environmental-only models relate species presence, abundance, or yield exclusively to environmental predictors. Spatially explicit models extend environmental models by explicitly modeling spatial dependence among observations.

Objectives: The aim of this report was to test a new methodological approach to better capture gradual spatial changes in wild boar relative abundance using spatially explicit models.

Methods:

We compared downscaled predictions from two models—environmental-only and spatially explicit—with estimates reported by ENETWILD (2022). The response variable was hunting yield abundance (HY) across Europe. To ensure comparability, we calculated the maximum annual number of individuals and selected covariates most frequently used in previous regional models. Hunting yields were modeled using a Negative Binomial framework to account for overdispersion, with expected yield modeled on the log scale as a linear combination of covariates plus a spatial random effect. Spatial dependence was modeled using a Nearest Neighbour Gaussian Process (NNGP) with exponential covariance. Predictions were downscaled to a 10×10 km grid within the species' known range. Model evaluation included:

- Summing predicted harvests
- Comparing uncertainty intervals (credible vs. confidence)
- Assessing spatial agreement via Spearman correlations
- Country-level comparisons for Spain, France, Italy, and Poland to account for data resolution differences

Results and conclusions:

Spatial random-effect models produce smooth continental patterns but are limited by non-stationarity and heterogeneous data resolution, leading to unreliable predictions in regions with coarse or uneven spatial units. While spatial effects help generate continuous abundance gradients, they do not resolve non-stationarity in species–

environment relationships. Large differences in observation unit size and quality strongly constrain prediction reliability, particularly where spatial decay parameters are smaller than distances between centroids. This limits the applicability of spatially explicit models at the continental scale unless territorial units are more homogeneous. Environmental-only and spatial models capture different aspects of wild boar distribution: environmental covariates largely drive abundance, while spatial effects improve predictions where high-quality data exist but may mask environmental influences. Low correlations among model types across regions highlight the need to explicitly account for non-stationarity and regional variability when modeling wild boar distribution at the European scale. The ENETWILD-consortium et al. (2024) model, which calibrates hunting bag data into wild boar density estimates, shows the strongest correlation with independent references and is currently the most reliable option for risk assessments that require spatially explicit wild boar density data. High-resolution hunting statistics are critical for producing realistic spatial patterns; where data resolution is low, models generate unreliable results, whereas areas with improved, high-resolution data (e.g. Sweden) yield spatial patterns consistent with ecological expectations.

1. Introduction

Spatial modelling is essential for active wildlife management, as well as improving ecological predictions. Accurate estimates of species abundance and distribution are fundamental to rapid decision-making, enabling managers to identify high-risk areas, prioritise surveillance and implement targeted interventions to prevent the spread of pathogens during disease outbreaks.

The wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) has become a model species for spatial distribution modelling in Europe. This is largely thanks to the ENETWILD consortium, funded and coordinated by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), which has compiled harmonised, high-resolution, continent-wide datasets on wild boar occurrence, relative abundance and hunting pressure. The availability of such comprehensive data has enabled the development and testing of advanced spatial modelling approaches, including hierarchical frameworks (Fernández-López et al. 2025). Progress in methodology achieved by using the wild boar as a model system is therefore likely to benefit the spatial modelling of other wildlife species, particularly those with fragmented or heterogeneous data sources.

The wild boar has a wide geographical distribution, enabling it to occupy environments with substantial variability. This ecological plasticity implies that its environmental relationships may not remain constant throughout its range — a condition known as non-stationarity, i.e., the same environmental condition can mean different things in different places. Previous studies have developed separate spatial distribution and abundance models for different regions to address the challenges posed by shifting species-environment relationships (Acevedo et al. 2014; ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2019; Ruiz-Rodríguez et al. 2022). Based on hunting yield data, these models account for regional effects and provide more reliable estimates. However, regional models may fail to accurately represent continuous spatial gradients (Cushman et al. 2010). Consequently, predictions based on these models may result in abrupt spatial patterns (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2022). Environmental-only models relate species presence, abundance, or yield exclusively to environmental predictors (once environmental variables are accounted for, observations are independent in space). Spatially explicit models extend environmental models by explicitly modeling spatial dependence among observations (species distributions are shaped not only by measured environment). This is done by adding a spatial random effect or spatial smooth to the model. Spatially explicit models have demonstrated promising predictive performance in capturing gradual spatial changes (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2020; Norberg et al. 2019) but have not yet been assessed at a continental scale.

The aim of this report was to test a new methodological approach to better capture gradual spatial changes in wild boar relative abundance using spatially explicit models.

2. Background and terms of reference

This contract/grant was awarded by EFSA to: Università degli Studi di Torino (UNITO). Contract/Grant title: Wildlife and One Health: wildlife ecology, health surveillance and interaction with livestock, human population and environment, contract number: OC/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01.

This report covers work package 4.1A of specific contract 03, which details the production of wildlife abundance models at European scale, including an update model for wild boar abundance by December 2025 based on hunting data. This report complements the report entitled "Using the latest data to model wild boar abundance at high resolution", which provides an update on the estimated wild boar distribution and abundance based on the most up to date density and occurrence data in Europe. The report is to be published on Zenodo and should include R scripts of the model properly documented and map of each species individually stored.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Data

The response variable for modelling wild boar was hunting yield abundance (HYs) across Europe. To compare with last published models, we calculated the maximum number of individuals annually hunted within 2015-2021 hunting seasons.

The covariates that were used more frequently as predictors when fitting the individual regional models (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2022) were selected for this report (see Table 1). Therefore, we considered the mean diurnal range (bio2; Worldclim 2, Fick & Hijmans, 2017), the mean altitude (USGS Space Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) GL30; <https://lta.cr.usgs.gov/SRTM1Arc>), the land use variables mainly related with forestry landscape composition (SA/CCI-LC project version v2.0.7; ESA, 2017). Previous expert evaluations determined some wrong predictions of wild boar abundance in West Europe when not considering *Eucalyptus spp.* plantations, as they are considered like forest by telemetry-derived cartographic variables, and suitability indexes calculated for those areas can be misleading. For this reason, we also considered as a predictor the percentage of *Eucalyptus spp.* as dominant species obtained from Brus et al. (2011) (European Forest Institute <https://www.efi.int/knowledge/maps/treespecies>). Moreover, given the differences in spatial resolution between the HYs, we also included the area as a covariate log

transformed in the model. This variable was indirectly used when modelling previous reports, as the response variable was wild boar density, that is, harvested number of individuals divided by the area size of the territory they were contained. Raster predictor layers and grid polygons were managed using QGIS 3.4 and *sf v1.0-21* R packages (Pebesma, 2018).

We found no evidence of multicollinearity among the selected predictors using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF); all VIF values were below 2 (Zuur et al. 2010).

All covariates were standardized using their mean and standard deviation.

Table 1: Variables used to model the spatial pattern of wild boar abundance.

Code	Variable description	Code	Variable description
BIO2	Mean diurnal range (mean of monthly (max temp - min temp))	ALT	Mean altitude
AREA	Area of sampling unit	Eu	Percentage of <i>Eucalyptus sp.</i>
lc_10	Cropland, rainfed	lc_30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)
lc_40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	lc_90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needle leaved)
lc_100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	lc_130	Grassland

3.2. Models based on hunting yield data

A Negative Binomial distribution was used for modelling HYs, $N_i \sim NB(\mu_i, \kappa)$, where N_i is the expected relative number of animals in a location i (with $i = 1, 2, \dots, I$; $I = 38494$), μ_i is the expected hunting yield value which vary in space according to covariates, and κ is the overdispersion parameter.

We defined the expected hunting yield in log scale to be a linear function of the covariates and a spatial random effect $\omega(s_i)$:

$$\log(\mu_i) = \beta * X_i + \omega(s_i),$$

where β are the linear effect of covariates (bio2, alt, Eu, lc10, lc30, lc40, lc90, lc100, lc130, area_log) and $\omega(s_i)$ is a spatial random effect.

The spatial random effect was specified through a Nearest Neighbor Gaussian Process (NNGP; Datta et al. 2016), which enables the expected response to vary smoothly across space and in relation to the covariates. This approach relies on a spatial covariance matrix, which was defined by an exponential function. The exponential function uses the Euclidean distance between locations and a set of spatial parameters (θ): the variance parameter, σ^2 , and the spatial decay parameter, ϕ .

$$\omega(s_i) \sim MVN(0, C)$$

$$C(s, s', \theta)$$

When θ defined by the exponential function: $\rho(s, s') = \sigma^2 * \exp(-\phi * d_{Eucl})$

The model was fitted in a Bayesian framework using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithms with the spAbundance 0.2.2 R package (Doser et al. 2024). We used normal prior for beta coefficients (mean=0 and var=1), uniform prior for kappa (a=0, b=100), uniform prior for ϕ (a=0.0470 and b=0.2) and inverse gamma for σ^2 (a =2 and $\beta=1$). We run three chains (length=100,000, burning=10,000, and thinning parameter=10). Model convergence was assessed by visual inspection of

traceplots, the Gelman-Rubin diagnosis R_{hat} ($0.9 < R_{hat} < 1.1$; Gelman & Rubin, 1992) and the Effective Sample Size (ESS; Gelman et al. 2025; Vehtarh et al. 2021). The model required approximately 4.57 days (6580 min) to complete the run on a computer equipped with 64 GB of RAM and 2.90GHz processor.

Model output was downscaled to make predictions at 10x10km using EAA grid (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/eea-reference-grids-2>). The predictions were made with the linear effects of covariates (environmental only) and with the linear effects of covariates and the spatial random effect (spatially explicit). Predictions were only projected inside of the recognized distribution range (Scandura et al. 2022).

3.3. Comparison of models based on hunting yield

We compared the downscaled predictions (environmental only and spatially explicit) with those reported in ENETWILD-consortium et al. (2022).

Quantitatively, we assessed the predictions by summing the predicted harvested values for each downscaled model. For the model developed in this report, we also compared the predicted credible intervals values with the confidence interval of the previous GLM model.

To evaluate spatial patterns, we computed Spearman correlations between predictions. Moreover, we performed specific comparisons for Spain, France, Italy, and Poland. The countries were selected to account for differences in the resolution of their reported datasets, ranging from the finest reported observation units (hunting grounds) to broader units (NUTS2). To compare the outputs of the models at a national level, we compared the respective model predictions (i.e. the predicted number of wild boars hunted) by country against the calibrated abundance (i.e. the total number of wild boar), according to ENETWILD-consortium et al. (2024), using Spearman correlations. The same comparison was performed against the national hunting bag (pre-ASF for infected countries; data from ENETWILD-consortium et al. (2024)). The countries for which all the necessary data were available within the wild boar distribution range were Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, the Czech Republic, Germany, Estonia, Greece, Spain, Finland, France, Croatia, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Latvia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Sweden, Slovenia and Slovakia (25 countries in total).

4. Results

Our results showed that 80% of the variables used to fit the model were not included in the zero credible interval, which indicates their importance for model construction (see Table 2). The model results also showed that the variance parameter was the largest of all the linear effects of the covariates. All the model parameters, except for

the intercept which exhibited poor mixing, reached convergence (see Table 2 and Fig. S1).

Prediction patterns from spatially explicit models appear similar for certain countries, such as Spain, but differ for others, such as Russia, when compared with the previous model. Environmental-only models appear to produce a pattern more similar to that of the previous model, except for Russia (see Fig. 1). Nevertheless, this model's predicted densities (individuals/km²) are substantially lower and display a narrower credible interval than the other two models (see Fig. 2).

Table 2. Covariate estimates from the negative binomial model.

	Mean	SD	2.5%	50%	97.5%	Rhat	ESS
Abundance (log scale):							
(Intercept)	3.2626	0.0411	3.1863	3.2628	3.3416	1.1328	52
bio_02	-0.0245	0.0264	-0.0788	-0.0231	0.0246	1.0894	164
elev	-0.1058	0.0205	-0.1461	-0.1058	-0.0659	1.0718	253
lc40	0.0801	0.0093	0.0620	0.0800	0.0986	1.0114	1472
Eucmean	-0.0204	0.0104	-0.0408	-0.0204	-0.0001	1.0019	1196
lc10	-0.1822	0.0110	-0.2036	-0.1821	-0.1603	1.0545	1029
lc30	0.0116	0.0087	-0.0051	0.0116	0.0293	1.0091	1619
lc90	0.0573	0.0098	0.0379	0.0573	0.0762	1.0449	543
lc100	0.2094	0.0096	0.1904	0.2094	0.2280	1.0212	1384
lc130	0.0259	0.0085	0.0091	0.0259	0.0427	1.0625	995
area_log_st	1.0552	0.0132	1.0286	1.0558	1.0803	1.0204	345
Spatial Covariance:							
sigma.sq	1.3864	0.0298	1.3295	1.3860	1.4453	1.0032	1433
phi	0.0486	0.0000	0.0486	0.0486	0.0487	1.0012	13281
NB overdispersion:							
Kappa	1.6984	0.0255	1.6493	1.698	1.749	1.0109	995

As for the comparison of outputs of the models at a national level (Figure 1), against the calibrated abundance (i.e. the total number of wild boar) and the national hunting bag (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2024):

- The environmental model presented the lowest levels of correlation (though still significant, $p < 0.01$) with both the predicted number of wild boars by Country (Spearman = 0.488) and the recorded number hunted (Spearman = 522). The

total number of animals hunted (3,910,000) was very similar to the actual figure (3,970,275).

- The spatial model correlated better ($p < 0.01$) with the predicted number of wild boars by Country (Spearman = 0.606) and presented the best correlation with the recorded number of wild boars hunted (0.746). The total number of predicted wild boars hunted (6,597,493) was approximately double the actual number reported (3,970,275).
- The ENETWILD-consortium et al. (2022) reference model correlated most strongly with the predicted number of wild boars by Country (Spearman = 0.672) and showed a high correlation with the recorded number of wild boars hunted (0.645). The total number of animals hunted (9,950,943) was approximately three times higher than the actual figure. We remark this model correlates well with EOW density predictions (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2024) and therefore the calibration into density value solves the issue of depending on abundance values (such as hunting yields).

In terms of spatial patterns, it was notable that, for the spatial model in countries, we predicted unrealistic spotted patterns where hunting bag resolution was low (e.g. in France and Germany). While the environmental-only model and the previous model (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2022) presented similar patterns in Central and Southern Europe, there were large areas at the northern border of the wild boar's distribution range where densities were higher than expected (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2025, see values of densities estimated by the EOW therein). We present in Annex 1 an updated summary of existing models for distribution and abundance of wild boar, including a description of model inputs, the modelling approach, the model outputs, the model validation, the main application of the model for ENETWILD and factors limiting the use by ENETWILD, as well as a link to the outputs of the recommended model (<https://zenodo.org/records/10809293>).

Continuous gradient of relative abundance of wild boars in Europe

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Continuous gradient of relative abundance of wild boars in Europe

Figure 1. Model output downscaled to make predictions at 10x10km using EAA grid). The predicted harvested wild boar (individuals/km²) were made with the linear effects of covariates (environmental only, upper left) and with the linear effects of covariates and the spatial random effect (spatially explicit, upper right map). The ENETWILD-consortium et al. (2022) is shown (bottom left). The spatial resolution of hunting bag yield used for modelling is shown for each country (bottom right).

Figure 2. The total predicted number of harvested wild boars in the 10 x 10 km grid cell is shown for the two predictions: environmental only (light blue), spatially explicit (blue), and ENETWILD et al. (dark blue). The dot points show the sum of the median total predicted values. The error bars show the sum of the lower (2.5) and upper (97.5) credible intervals.

Figure 3. General Spearman correlation plot of predicted harvested wild boar in the 10 x 10 km grid cell for the Enetwild 2022 model (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2022), environ (environmental only) and spatially explicit for all Europe (a), Spain (b), France (c), Italy (d), Poland (e).

Correlation in spatial patterns (Figure 3) seems to vary depending on the scale of comparison. At a broad scale, predictions from the environmental-only and spatially explicit models seem to have more similar patterns, which would indicate a general concordance between locations with low and high species values. At national scale, the correlation between predicted models differs. Spain exhibited a moderate correlation between all approaches, whereas other countries, such as France or Italy, showed lower correlation values between the environmental-only and spatially explicit predictions. In contrast to these countries, Poland displayed the highest correlation between environmental and spatial predictions, while correlations with the regional approach were lower for both.

5. Discussion

Previous studies on wild boar have developed separate models to address the challenges posed by shifting species–environment relationships. These models account for potential regional variations and improve the reliability of estimates (Acevedo et al. 2014; ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2019; Ruiz-Rodríguez et al. 2022). However, regional models can produce inaccurate predictions of continuous environmental gradients between regions, which is undesirable (Cushman et al. 2010; ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2022). To address this, we developed a continent-scale model that incorporates spatial effects, and in this report, we describe its strengths and limitations.

Spatial random effects and the centroid-based representation of observation units

For the first time, we applied a model incorporating spatial random effects to capture gradual spatial variation at a continental scale. This type of model has previously demonstrated promising predictive performance at smaller spatial scales (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2020; Norberg et al. 2019). However, it should be noted that adding a spatial random effect does not account for non-stationarity in the model; the relationship between the environment and species will remain constant throughout the study area. Therefore, we expected the signs of the model coefficients (positive or negative) to differ from those in previous reports, since the models in these reports were fitted individually, allowing greater flexibility in the environment-species relationship. Our results suggest that the addition of a spatial random effect produces a smoother pattern, with a continuous gradient of wild boar abundance across Europe (see Fig. 1). However, the patterns produced also exhibited unusual shapes in countries with low spatial resolution data (e.g. France and Russia).

These shapes can be explained because, when constructing a spatially explicit model, the covariance matrix requires the location of the coordinates for each unit. When using an exponential function, the covariance matrix is defined by the spatial variance parameter, σ^2 , a decay parameter, ϕ , and the Euclidean distance. The decay parameter controls the spatial autocorrelation range. If the spatial autocorrelation range is smaller than the Euclidean distance between the coordinate locations, the predictions may 'lose' the spatial effects calculated for the model. In our case, we used the centroids of the observation units to calculate the covariance matrix and the centroids of each cell grid to make predictions. Centroid cell grid locations closer to the centroid of the observation units may produce more reliable predictions, whereas longer distances between them, outside of the decay parameter range, may result in less reliable predictions. Consequently, predictions based on this model may produce erroneous values when the spatial resolution of the territorial units is greater than the distance considered by the spatial decay parameter (ϕ), indicating that patterns obtained in countries such as France, Finland and Russia must not be considered.

Conversely, countries such as Spain, which have high-quality fine-scale data, seem to have a pattern close to the known distribution of species abundance. Therefore, it seems challenging to use a spatially varying coefficient to predict a continuous, gradual pattern across Europe when observation units differ greatly in size (e.g. from 0.01 km² to 104,163 km²). Some studies have already highlighted the difficulties of producing reliable estimates and predictions when using large observation units of HYS. They emphasize that low-resolution data may hamper the applicability of this information for wildlife management at finer scales (Bauder et al. 2021; Gilbert et al. 2021). Other approaches, such as those involving spatially varying coefficients (SVC; see, for example, Doser et al. 2024; Finley, 2011), may offer greater flexibility in modelling the relationship between species and their environment, and allow for the consideration of non-stationarity, as in regional models. However, it is likely that differences in spatial resolution affect predictions.

An alternative approach would be to generate predictions based solely on environmental factors, which would mitigate the challenges posed by heterogeneous territorial units. This approach generally improves the spatial pattern, demonstrating that environmental factors largely determine species abundance. However, in countries with high-quality data, such as Spain, the pattern obtained using spatial random effects achieved higher correlation with the previous report to that obtained using environmental covariates alone. Conversely, predicted values based solely on environmental covariates are lower than those obtained when incorporating spatial random effects, since the variability explained by the spatial parameters is excluded. Furthermore, the addition of a spatial random effect can obscure the impact of environmental covariates (Hodges & Reich, 2010; Keil et al. 2014). Therefore, constructing a model with a spatial random effect but making predictions without it may increase the predictive capability of patterns but may lead to inaccurate predictions of quantity (see Fig. 2).

Country-level evidence of non-stationarity and data resolution constraints

Additionally, to address non-stationarity, we assessed the correlations between the predictions to quantify the differences in the spatial patterns in relation to the model structure (i.e. individual, spatially explicit and environmental-only models).

At the continental scale, spatially explicit predictions showed a moderate correlation with environmental-only and individual models, whereas environmental-only models exhibited a low negative correlation with individual models. This may be because incorporating spatial random effects can confound the effect of environmental covariates (Hodges & Reich, 2010; Keil et al. 2014). Consequently, predictions based solely on environmental coefficients may fail to account for certain effects that are

absorbed by the spatial component when it is included. Furthermore, these differences could be exacerbated by the fact that environmental-only predictions were generated using a single set of covariates across Europe, whereas individual model predictions relied on region-specific covariates and coefficients. Therefore, it may be limiting to compare spatial patterns derived from models that do not share the same covariate structure, which could be particularly evident in country-level correlation comparisons.

While there was a moderate correlation between the environmental-only and individual models in Spain, France and Italy, there was none in Poland. This may be because environmental conditions in Poland differ from those in the aforementioned countries in terms of both the magnitude of the effects of the covariates and the variables used to build the models. This highlights the importance of considering non-stationarity when modelling at a European scale, since the spatial random effect appears unable to capture all environmental variability that cannot be distinguished by the covariates within a single model. The low correlation observed between environmental-only and spatially explicit models in France and Italy could be explained by the size and heterogeneity of the territorial units, respectively. In France, issues with predictions from the spatially explicit model may arise because the distance considered by the spatial decay parameter is smaller than the spatial resolution of the territorial units. This makes differences in predictions more likely when predicting at a finer resolution (10x10 km). In Italy, the spatially explicit model does not correlate with either the environmental-only or the individual model. One possible reason for this is that the data available for this country are heterogeneous. Although including a spatial latent effect may improve predictions, it can also lead to overfitting the data. This has been found to be especially sensitive to spatial gaps when making predictions (unpublished results). Consequently, achieving more homogeneous territorial units, as well as avoiding spatial gaps, seems essential when applying this approach.

Comparison of outputs

The ENETWILD-consortium et al. (2022) reference model correlated most strongly with the predicted number of wild boars by Country and showed a high correlation with the recorded number of wild boars hunted (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2024). We remark this model correlates well with EOW density predictions (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2024) and has been calibrated into density value. This allow using density rather than abundance values (such as hunting yield predictions). Regarding the spatial patterns of model outputs, it was notable that, for the spatial model, we obtained unrealistic spotted patterns where hunting bag resolution was low (such as in France and Germany), which prevented their use for high-resolution risk

assessment. However, where good resolution data was available, the spatial patterns were in line with expectations, as in Sweden, where higher resolution data was recently incorporated into modelling compared to the previous model (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2022). This illustrates the importance of collecting and sharing high-resolution hunting statistics for wild boar to develop reliable spatial models. While the environmental-only model and the previous model ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2022) presented similar patterns in Central and Southern Europe, there were large areas at the northern border of the wild boar's distribution range where densities were higher than expected (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2024, and values of densities of the EOW therein). Overall, this evaluation of patterns indicates that the ENETWILD-consortium et al. (2024) model which calibrates hunting bags to densities, is currently the best option for supporting further risk assessments where spatial data on wild boar population density is required.

6. Conclusions

- Spatial random-effect models can produce smooth continental patterns but are limited by data resolution and non-stationarity. Incorporating spatial random effects allows the generation of a continuous gradient of wild boar abundance across Europe, but this approach does not address non-stationarity in species–environment relationships. As a result, predictions can be unreliable or misleading in regions with coarse or heterogeneous spatial units.
- Heterogeneous spatial resolution strongly constrains the reliability of large-scale predictions. Large differences in the size and quality of observation units lead to erroneous or unusable predictions in several countries, particularly where spatial decay parameters are smaller than the distances between centroids. This limits the applicability of spatially explicit and spatially varying coefficient models at the continental scale unless territorial units are more homogeneous.
- Environmental-only and spatially explicit models capture different aspects of wild boar distribution, highlighting the need to account for non-stationarity. Environmental covariates largely determine wild boar abundance, but spatial random effects can improve predictions where high-quality data exist, while also potentially masking environmental effects. Differences and low correlations among model types across regions underscore the importance of explicitly considering non-stationarity and regional variability when modelling wild boar distribution at the European scale.
- The ENETWILD-consortium et al. (2024) model, which calibrates hunting bag data into wild boar density estimates (from ENETWILD-consortium et al. (2022)), shows the strongest correlation with independent references and is currently the most reliable option for risk assessments that require spatially explicit wild boar density data.

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- High-resolution hunting statistics are critical for producing realistic spatial patterns; where data resolution is low, models generate unreliable results, whereas areas with improved, high-resolution data (e.g. Sweden) yield spatial patterns consistent with ecological expectations.

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8. Supplementary information

S1. Assessing model convergence

Figure S1. Trace and density plots, Rhat and ESS for assessing convergence of the modelling approach.